

PROCEEDINGS OF THE GAMES INTERSECTIONAL SYMPOSIUM

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The symposium brought together artists, researchers, designers, and community organizers working at and within the intersections of games, identity, and justice.

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Social Innovation and Video Games: Exploring Implications for Learning and Teaching

by Patrick Gregori & Milica Marković, University of Klagenfurt

Sliders for Everything (Except Gender): A Critique of Gender Norms in Video Game Character Creators through 'Your Average Character Creator'

by Eileen Carette

Disruption through Strategic Game Design: Challenging Caste Transmission Using Interactive Media

by Srikanth Sundaram

In Other Bodies - Inhabiting the Nonhuman Body in Video Games as a Means for Empathy

by Florian Schäfer

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In Other Bodies
*Inhabiting the Nonhuman Body in Video Games as a Means for
Empathy*

Florian Schäfer
Master in British and North American Cultural Studies

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	1
1. Introduction	2
2. Plot Summary and Central Mechanics	3
3. Video Games and Prosthetic Affect	5
4. <i>In Other Waters</i> and the Posthuman	9
5. Non-Sentient First Contact Fiction and the Inherent Value of life	11
6. Futurity and Ecocriticism	16
7. Conclusion	20
Works Cited	22

1. Introduction

Humanity has mostly depleted all resources on Earth and the solution for this man-made problem might not lie on the blue planet at all. This is also the starting point for Jump Over the Edge's *In Other Waters*. In a not nearly specified future marine biologist Ellery Vas travels to the planet Gliese 667Cc and completely unexpectedly finds life there. The problem facing humanity might not seem all that futuristic to the player, and so might one of the biggest challenges any solution for it has to face: to fix the problem, the known systems of life for a large part of the population would have to change. As Megan Condis explains through various sources and the analysis of the video game Heaven's Vault this is a dire situation, since in most cases in which people are faced with the decision between destruction and a sudden and grave change in their known systems and preferences, they usually end up destroyed.

The game then charts Ellery's journey through these oceans, accompanied by the player, taking the role of the AI that controls her diving suit. The objective of this analysis of *In Other Waters* is to interrogate whether the game uses the affordances of its medium in a constructive way to create an ecocritical theme. As a video game *In Other Waters* is in a unique position to create embodied emotions, which will here be developed under the term prosthetic affect, relating to the representations it contains. It achieves this by utilising the interactions between its various modes of mediation, such as audio, and visual, but also interactivity to create this embodied experience. In combination with the game's plot, this means it lends itself to a posthuman and ecocritical reading which interrogates the destructive effect of humanity on nature as well as its place and possible responsibilities concerning it. Another important element in the analysis of the game will be whether the interaction between gameplay elements and narrative fiction is a constructive or a disruptive process. For this, I will first summarise the plot of the game as well as its general gameplay to be able to effectively reference these in my later analysis.

The summary will be followed by developing the emotional reactions of players regarding video game narratives as an embodied, physical experience. Developing the term prosthetic affect, I will be following the ideas of productive prosthetic experiences in memories and imagination set up by Alison Landsberg and Peter Boxall as well as Eugénie Shinkle's understanding of affect as it is created by video games. The objective here is to point out how video games can increase the urgency of their themes by creating profound emotional experiences.

The next step will then be to show how this prosthetic affect supports *In Other Waters* in developing posthuman themes along the lines of discourses set up by, for example, Francesca

Ferrando. A key element in these parts of the posthuman discourse is that the anthropocentrism of other discourses, such as those on transhumanism, is swapped out for decentralised equality of importance for all living beings. Here it will be shown how *In Other Waters* not only does this through narrative elements that remind the player of their non-central role in the ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc but also through the way it communicates its narrative and audio-visual representations to the player, as well as gameplay elements.

Finally, building on the idea of prosthetic affect and the posthuman themes that the game develops through them I will show how these affordances can be effectively used to set up an ecocritical theme that is not completely subverted by the gameplay elements. Alenda Chang, in her Manifesto for Environmental Game Design, argues this is often the case for video games. Thus she suggests that an ecocritical game would have to develop new ways of interaction between the player and the world of the game if they wanted their themes to be completely carried over to the audience. The point of this analysis is to consider whether this is the case for the modes in which *In Other Waters* has their player interact with its simulated deep-sea ecosystem. The analysis will weigh the interactions of the narrative's posthuman and ecocritical themes against the medium's capability of creating embodied emotional experiences and then consider whether these interactions are aided or hindered by their relationship to the interactions demanded by the gameplay to complete the story. The result will be an in-depth assessment of the effectiveness of the ecocritical and posthuman themes of *In Other Waters*.

2. Plot Summary and Central Mechanics

In Other Waters is a narrative-driven, text-focused video game developed by one-person game development studio Jump over the Age, consisting solely of Gareth Damian Martin, which was published by Fellow Traveller in early 2020. The plot of the game has the player take control of an AI, tasked with controlling the diving suit piloted by marine biologist Ellery Vas, who has come on her own to the planet Gliese 667Cc in search of her former co-worker and partner Minae. Shortly into her underwater exploration of Gliese, it becomes apparent that contrary to Ellery's expectations the planet is not uninhabited but home to a lush flora and fauna. Giving in to her professional curiosity Ellery immediately decides to catalogue as much of the ecosystem as possible while continuing her search. While traversing the oceans of Gliese 667Cc the pair also come across the aftermath of a recent near-extinction event as well as traces of what might have been sentient life, which was eradicated in the aforementioned event.

As she finally finds Minae deep in the oceans of Gliese 667Cc Ellery learns that her friend has mutated due to unknown reasons and is now capable of surviving deep within the ocean without any technological assistance, seemingly indefinitely. While Ellery and the AI do take her back into the research station that functions as their base, there is no verbal communication possible with Minae. Still, after being initially taken aback at the physical changes Ellery comes to terms with them and continues her exploration of Gliese 667Cc.

This is where she starts to find evidence of former human activity on the planet, as the company for which Minae had been working on the planet had set up several research stations deep within the oceans in hopes of finding ways to use the flora and fauna to support the by now failing resources of Earth. Here they learn that the near-extinction of the organisms of Gliese 667Cc was the result of these experiments. It is further revealed that the AI the player is controlling was created in these facilities by combining human technology with findings of the possible sentient inhabitants of the planet, which are dubbed as The Artificers. At this point, the player has to choose whether they want to frame this revelation as being the result of the AI not knowing this itself, or whether it kept this fact hidden due to an ingrained distrust against humans.

Finally, the pair make their way into the ruins of the Ocean Brain, the facility that caused the near-cataclysm on Gliese 667Cc. They find the machine destroyed, but also encounter what might be a surviving, young artificer, which however flees before they can interact in any meaningful way. After this Ellery decides to spend her time collecting as much data as possible on the ecosystem of Gliese before other humans will discover the planet and more than likely destroy it while exploiting the planet's resources in favour of sustaining Earth.

In all this, the player is tasked with controlling Ellery's diving suit, which means they have to chart courses through the ocean by selecting one of several possible destinations, as well as keeping the energy and oxygen supply of the suit stable by utilising the spores and microorganisms they encounter and collect during their exploration. Another use for these spores and organisms is to strategically place them in certain parts of the areas which they explore to use the natural interactions between the creatures of Gliese 667Cc to open up new paths. Further, microbes and spores can also be brought back to the home base, where Ellery can analyse them, which results in the game building up an ever deeper encyclopaedia of the life on Gliese 667Cc. During these travels and the constant narration that Ellery provides the player is sometimes allowed to respond verbally to her, though the decisions made in these interactions have no impact on the plot and it is possible for the player to choose not to communicate at all in most instances.

Since the player is taking on the role of an AI, their perception in all of this is restricted to the necessary minimum: two-dimensional topographical maps of the surroundings and several symbols, all held in very few colours that signify objects, life forms as well as the few sources of danger the game contains. There is also a HUD that allows the player to chart a course, search for and extract smaller creatures and spores and interact with the generator and oxygen tank of the diving suit. Outside of this the human player of the game has to fully rely on Ellery's verbal descriptions as well as the few sketches she adds to fully analysed specimens that have been brought to the home base in their aesthetic evaluation of Gliese 667Cc.

3. Video Games and Prosthetic Affect

The prosthetic properties of narrative media have been discussed for some time now, as is for example the case with Alison Landsberg's notion of prosthetic memory or Peter Boxall's prosthetic imagination. Central for both of these concepts is that the effects of the narratives which are encountered by the audience are embodied (Landsberg 148), in the sense that while they are created through a mediated event they are still physically experienced by the individual observer (Landsberg 155), and that they are consequently productive. For Landsberg, this is very important in the way that mediated experiences can create empathy, which she here delimits from sympathy by stating that the former is an intellectual appreciation of the other and their experiences, whereas the latter can result in flattening the nuances of identity by transposing the experiences of one person upon another (147). Boxall works along similar lines when he explains that one of the prosthetic capabilities of mimesis is that it bridges the gap between the internal conceptions and expectations of the individual and the deviating external realities (14).

As a result, they both argue from different perspectives that an important element of mediated experiences is how they confront the audience with the other in a way that impresses deeply personalised experiences upon the individual and as such, they are highly effective as tools for creating identification and empathy with others. That this function of mediated narratives is present especially strong in video games has already been observed by Alenda Chang, who claims in *Green Computer and Video Games: An Introduction* that they are highly effective at creating involvement since they do not only argue through argumentative, evidence-based logic but emotional triggers and affective dynamics (8). For Eugénie Shinkle this is the case since many video games seek purposefully to incorporate the body of the player into the experience of playing the game (27 – 30). As a result, she argues that affect, what she calls the 'rush' that is felt while

playing, is central to the understanding of a video game since here affect is another level of signification for the medium (22). To Shinkle, the physical is always involved in the experience of a video game as body, mind, and the mediated world work together as a feedback system shaping a perceptual experience (30). Daniel Johnson in *Animated Frustration or the Ambivalence of Player Agency* also describes how games can impress physically felt emotions upon the audience while playing. Using the examples of *Steel Battalion: Heavy Armor* and *Papers, Please* he talks about the interactions between the body and the narrative of a game as the control schemes and physical interactions demanded by them frustrate the player in different ways. He does, however, not talk about possible readings of this as productive in the development of the wider narrative of a specific video game as a complete artefact that creates an experience through the interaction of its various points of interaction. For Johnson frustration is a disrupting force to the intended interaction between player and game and therefore carries mostly negative connotations that distance the game from some intended effect (593). Conceptions such as Shinkle's application of affect and also Landsberg's and Boxall's focus on embodied experiences and the effects thereof however could allow for a reading of frustration in video games as a productive force. The tensions between the intended input and the results, which might or might not differ from the expected outcome, can greatly increase the affective response that is created by a moment of gameplay and while Shinkle's term of 'rush' calls to mind the elating excitement of success after a period of hardship in a game it can also be extended to all other emotional responses that the interaction with a video game might impress on the player, be it frustration, elation, suspension or boredom.

Consequently, video games do not only produce Landsberg's prosthetic memories of the other that are impressed on the audience or Boxall's prosthetic imagination which uses mimesis to bridge the gap between the internally perceived and an external reality but they are also capable of creating prosthetic affect: through the interaction of their visual, aural, and narrative elements with the ongoing interaction demanded by gameplay mechanics video games can physically impress strong emotions into their audience in a manner that is not necessarily open to other media. Through their immense diversity in modes through which video games can engage their players, they have numerous possibilities to create affective reactions through visual and aural aesthetics, the narrative they communicate or the way the gameplay has the audience interact with the simulated world. Further, the connections between these elements allow for interesting interconnections. Each time there will be a perceivable continuation or tension between any of these elements the overall experience will be modified.

That not all of these moments of prosthetic affect has to be rooted in some intense feeling, as Shinkle's usage of the term 'rush' might seem to imply, can be seen in *In Other Waters*. Very little in the game could be seen as capable of creating the feeling of excitement that is often expected when it comes to video games. The visual representation of Gliese 667Cc is almost aggressively minimalist in the way it is reduced to nothing but a vague topographical map and the few HUD elements needed for the diving suit operated by the player to fully function. This decision of reductionism is continued in the colour scheme which has little more to offer than shades of blue, yellow, green and red. In depicting what is supposed to be a lush and vibrant world in these abstract modes the game very much breaks with the way video games tend to depict nature according to Alenda Chang's *Back to Virtual Farming: Gleaming the Agriculture-Management Game*, where she points out that the medium tends to depict nature in an almost pastoral mode of fictional beauty, disconnected from all labour and degradation. While it could be argued that the minimalism of the visual representation of *In Other Waters* does not only avoid depicting unproblematic natural beauty it also at the same time removes its tools to show labour and degradation, it sidesteps this problem by making the human narrator Ellery Vas a marine biologist. Her interest in her surroundings is deeply rooted in the interconnection of the ecosystem she is exploring and especially any kind of external danger done by human interaction is pointed out by her with great urgency.

The visual representations of the game are also productive for how the game facilitates identification with the player character: an AI tasked with supervising and steering an extraterrestrial diving suit might just not need any superfluous information. All but topography and possible sources of danger become uninteresting and even these are represented in only the most abstracted, easy to read manner. It also means that they will pay close attention to Ellery's narration, as it is their only window into what the world of Gliese 667Cc looks like through human eyes, therefore helping to focus her character in isolation but most of all the necessary collaboration between human and AI in fully understanding the new surroundings. The gradual discovery of the planet thus carries a moment of satisfaction itself for the player, an embodied experience in line with the idea of prosthetic affect developed here.

Another element through which video games can facilitate prosthetic affect is the visual representation of the game world and in *In Other Waters* for the human player, here pushed into the prosthetic body of an AI, limited perception is a central element that can become one of the moments of frustration that Johnson talked about but did not fully analyse regarding their productive capabilities. As soon as it turns out that Gliese 667Cc is the home to extraterrestrial life the suit's pilot Ellery starts to describe the lush flora and fauna surrounding the player at any given

time. She marvels at what she sees, makes assumptions and offers hypotheses that the player has no way of verifying. Even as over the course of the game several illustrations are added to these descriptions, they only offer partial insights into the textual descriptions of the beauty of the oceans found in another world. The tension between what is described in the text and what is perceivable by the audience, the deliberate frustration of curiosity, is highly productive for the overall narrative and themes of the game, as it not only brings the AI and Ellery closer together in their exploration of the new environment but it also develops the theme of connection and cooperation between the two. Neither of them could fully appreciate and experience what the player finds here. Ellery would be incapable of surviving and exploring the uncharted depths on her own and while the AI could do this, its perception makes it incapable of fully appreciating the visual beauty that Ellery narrates. Interdependencies such as this that are created and expanded upon by the aesthetic simulation and the narrative descriptions of the game are also central to its ecocritical elements that will be discussed later.

Gameplay, and especially the physical interaction with the controls of the game, are another aspect of *In Other Waters* that help the game in developing prosthetic affect. While the game offers only very little in actual points of interaction and agency for the player, by this not necessarily fulfilling the expectations that the term video game usually contains for the audience, that repetition of simple commands, almost always without any pressure in the form of time constraints or negative consequences for a lack of success, effectively supports the narrative mood the game develops. Gliese 667Cc harbours only very few threats to the player and the plot and themes of the game are more interested in giving space for the contemplation of an alien world, the few interactions between Ellory and the AI and maybe most of all the way all of these systems interacts to create a larger whole in cooperating. By tasking the player with only a few and relatively simple tasks, travelling the ocean of Gliese 667Cc is turned into an almost meditative occupation as the player chooses their next destination, lines up the suit, reads Ellory's comments upon arrival and then goes on to repeat this process. When Shinkle uses a term such as 'rush' or Johnson speaks of 'frustration' this leads to expectations of strong and salient emotions but Shinkle later amends the metaphoric usage of 'rush' by stating that she uses affect not synonymous with emotions, as it often the case but to her, the affect of a game is related to its 'feel' and its 'intensity' (22). These terms might be more fitting as they allow for a wider range of connected emotions and in the case of *In Other Waters* the 'intensity' is deliberately low and the 'feel' decidedly contemplative. Both of which are modes of interaction that are strongly supported by the simple visuals, the calm music

and maybe more than anything by the simple motions the player is constantly repeating as they are imagining the seascape of Gliese 667Cc with the help of marine biologist Ellery Vas.

As shown in these examples it is prosthetic affect that makes the narratives of video games predisposed to connect the player to the experiences of the other. These embodied emotional connections are why Chang considers video games to be so effective for the creation of ecocritical narratives (Introduction 8). An important element here is that through the way they invite identification with others they can facilitate a movement of de-centring for the player as they create mediated yet still embodied experiences of the other. *In Other Waters* escalates this experience further as it places the player in the body of an AI that is also the result of the combination of human technology and alien life. In this, the game shows a strong connection to posthuman concepts which I will explore in the next chapter.

4. *In Other Waters* and the Posthuman

The strong identification with the other is a possible consequence of the predisposition of video games to generate prosthetic affect. In the case of *In Other Waters*, this affect is mostly created concerning the unnamed AI that the player is directly controlling as well as Ellery. For both of these, the player has complex insight into the emotional and experiential processes these characters encounter. In the case of the AI, this happens through direct interaction when the player can control the actions and by this express the will of the AI. For one the intentions, the player inscribes on the AI as a participant of the events are verbally narrated through the opportunities to directly communicate with their human passenger. However, decisions made in gameplay can also be considered to be important for the characterisation of the AI, as the player might choose to play them as reckless or careful, curious or focused on the task at hand. These opportunities at roleplaying can also increase the intensity of embodied experiences as the player might feel, for example, real and palpable frustration at not being able to navigate the dangers of Gliese 667Cc successfully. Another moment where the failure of intended play described by Johnson can be a constructive force for the narrative intent of the game.

Ellery is another nexus of narration, as she makes up for the sensory shortcomings of the player, replacing the lacking details of their HUD with her descriptions and comments. As she opens up to the AI, revealing her past and intentions the interior processes of Ellery also become more known to the player, even though they are still more removed from them as the AI itself. Ultimately, however, neither of them would be able to experience the oceans of Gliese 667Cc the

same way as the player if they were on their own. As a result *In Other Waters* develops a thematic focus on cooperation and especially how the presence of both AI and marine biologist are vital for the player to fully experience the world as they do. This symbiotic relationship between AI and pilot is also mirrored in the flora and fauna that Ellery is observing as she communicates how she sees processes of pollination, cooperation and interactions. *In Other Waters* takes great care to depict Gliese 667Cc as well as the two player characters not as disconnected entities, but as systems that interact and profit off each other.

The result of this focus on symbiosis is that the individual becomes de-centred. In her text on the various forms and discourses on trans- and posthumanism Francesca Ferrando calls de-centring and de-hierarchisation central tenets of posthuman movements (29). To her, the important element that separates posthumanism from transhumanism is that it is not focused on a vertical improvement resulting in the creation of a superior entity but instead intends to move away from anthropocentric perspectives that place humanity and its progress at the centre. *In Other Waters* directly illustrates these ideas as it has the player observe a world in which they are fully incidental but not necessarily unwelcome. The ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc is a complex interaction of many contributors, which the player has to learn to understand to effectively navigate the oceans, but it would just as well function without their presence. The absence of predators threatening the player is another element that helps the game to show interactions lacking any real hierarchies, as, unlike in many other games, the player is not forced to struggle for control over others. Instead, every participant of the ecosystem of Gliese, ultimately even the AI and Ellery as outsiders, play an important part in the continued existence of life on Gliese 667Cc.

That the struggle for control in other games does have grave effects on the narratives that can be depicted and, more importantly, how they are received, can be seen in Callum T. F. McMillan's *Posthumanism in Digital Culture*. Here he describes how studies of video games often focus on transhumanist ideas (21). This makes sense as the mechanics of many games have the players fight for the mastery of their environment. To do so they often offer them various methods of improving their tools or the player-character or characters themselves. This focus on improvement and hierarchical development lend itself well to readings following concepts following a traditional understanding of posthumanism as it was described by Ferrando. So it is specifically the deviations from standard gameplay mechanics of *In Other Waters* that allow the game to be decidedly posthuman in its equalising moments between different life forms. In her *Manifesto for Environmental Game Design* Alenda Chang also points out how for video games to be able to develop an ecocritical narrative games will have to develop a wider range of player-

environment interactions. Her example for this is the so-called walking simulators (73). The interesting element here seems to be that these games have often been criticised for their lack of interactivity but as we can see through *In Other Waters* the lack of direct action can also be a game mechanic and a statement, especially in the context of a game that labours to de-centre the human element. Here it can be highly productive in communicating the themes of a game as it offers a lack of or only minimal, interaction as a valid and valuable choice.

That *In Other Waters* rejects many questions that are often connected to transhumanist discourses in favour of an understanding of posthumanism built around symbiotic relations can also be seen in the character of Minae and to a certain extent in the origins of the AI. Ferrando as well as McMillan point out that the discourses on trans- and posthumanism inherently contain the question of humanity and its possible future disappearance. For McMillan, this is the question of whether the posthuman inextricably contains the extinction or disappearance of the human, though he seems to argue against this (13), and Ferrando specifically names Antihumanism as a movement that acknowledges the "death of Man" (31). As pointed out above *In Other Waters* depicts a world in which human presence is incidental at best and harmful at worst. The ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc does not require humans to function and would more than likely not notice the death of its few human visitors. The events surrounding Minae however show that Gliese's oceans and their development do not require the removal of mankind to continue to function. While the exact events around Minae's mutation are not elaborated what is clear is that the changes in her body, while initially disturbing to Ellery, are not harmful to her and allow her to better participate in the oceanic ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc as is seen in her ability to dive to great depths without a suit and to survive without an oxygen supply.

In this mutation, which brings her closer to the flora and fauna of her new home Minae shows that the development that is found in the game is not a transhuman development of hierarchical evolution that produces an improved version to replace the original but instead depicts a horizontal movement that allows the individual to further exist, even if in a new context. This focus on adaptation and hybridity can also be seen in the origins of the player AI, which is late in the game revealed to be the result of a combination of human technology and the now apparently extinct Artificers, which inhabited Gliese 667Cc until recently and were probably sentient. In this combination of heritages, the AI is like Minae another symbol for how existence in the oceans of the game is built on adaptation and cooperation but that these processes do not have to fully destroy the identity of those that become part of it. Thus *In Other Waters* directly rejects the violence that might be seen as inherent to transhumanist developments and instead offers an equalising,

posthumanist alternative. The decentralisation of human life in favour of hybrid development and most of all the symbiotic relations between the flora and fauna of Gliese 667Cc show that the game has an overt interest in ecological questions and as part of this uses its posthumanist perspectives to negotiate the value of non-human and non-sentient life, a question which I will explore next.

5. Non-Sentient First Contact Fiction and the Inherent Value of life

The posthumanist perspectives of *In Other Waters* result in the decentralisation of sentient, human life and consequently any hierarchy that argues that human life carries innate primacy over others is brought into question as well. These hierarchies are often an inherent element of both the fiction as well as the mechanics of video games, as Erik van Ooijen explains in his essay on the hunting and killing of animals in video games *On the Brink of Extinction*. Here he argues that games often use their systems to create a typology about which forms of violence are acceptable against whom and under which circumstances. To him, the result of these typologies often is that violence against animals is much more acceptable than it is against humans (33 – 34). This, according to him, is most of all facilitated by the fact that the bodies of animals are usually accepted as the source of resources such as meat, while those of humans are not, by this specifically turning animal bodies into objects (38). Van Ooijen also points out that animal life as a resource in video games is often infinite, which decreases the effect the player considers to have on their surroundings when they hunt them (41 – 43).

In Other Waters has a very different relationship to the non-human life it contains. One important factor in this is the human perspective that the game simulates to have the player perceive the alien life of Gliese 667Cc, specifically the fact that all emotional descriptors the game can offer are the result of Ellery's narration. Not only does this mean that the world is exclusively encountered in terms of the emotional interiority of a single person but even more important this person is a marine biologist, somebody who is assumed to have a deep emotional connection to animal life in the first place. Therefore the narration of the game, everything the player has in their way of perceiving this alien life outside of the AI's simple HUD, which mostly consists of abstract visualisations of the absence or presence of objects, is constantly emotionally charged and filled with ideas of observation and preservation. The human player, as a consequence of the limited visual representations of the game, is forced to rely on Ellery's descriptions to fulfil their human curiosity in what the exciting discoveries look like. The focus on the perspective of a scientist who is overwhelmed and fascinated by what she sees locks the perspective the player has on what they

encounter into a specific frame of reference. Ellery does not see the life of Gliese 667Cc as something to be hunted and exploited but instead constantly shows her will to observe and preserve and thus these themes become the emotional language of *In Other Waters*.

The way Ellery tends to analyse her surroundings also has another important implication for the negotiation of non-sentient life, namely her curiosity and scientific interest in the way the flora and fauna of Gliese 667Cc interact with each other. As already mentioned in its importance for the decentralisation of human life for the posthumanist perspectives of the game, the ecosystem that Ellery explores is depicted as an interlocking system of various life forms, interacting with each other, often in a symbiotic manner. Observations such as this are grounded in Ellery's interest as a scientist and for the game also important since they show that the life on this planet does not exist in any orbit around human interactions. For Ellery, the value of the life she encounters lies not in the way that she as a human can profit but in the beauty of their interactions with each other. Therefore her specific perspective as a biologist and her explicit interest in observing and understanding the ecosystem she encounters help *In Other Waters* to avoid the typologies of acceptable and unacceptable violence that van Ooijien sees in many other games since the voice in which it speaks is decidedly disinterested in exploiting them for profit. Instead, in charting the interactions of these life forms with each other in the absence of human interaction and depicting her feelings of awe and glee at this the game manages to give the non-sentient life of Gliese 667Cc inherent value, disconnected from any use or exchange functions. To Ellery the animals and plants of the ocean are beautiful and valuable simply because they exist, a framing that is further supported by this being depicted as the first human contact with alien life, showing the creatures of Gliese 667Cc to be unique and wondrous merely by being there, not because they represent the solution to some specified danger that drives the plot forward.

Gameplay takes a somewhat ambiguous role here. As already explained the interactions between player and game world that is facilitated by the mechanics of a video game are an important element in how the audience receives and interprets the fiction that is encoded within a game. Interactions such as this are why Alenda Chang argued that to carry a coherent ecocritical message they will need to develop new ways of interaction that do not disrupt the themes of the narrated plot (Introduction 73). *In Other Waters*, limited as the interaction between player and Gliese 667Cc made possible through gameplay mechanics might seem, attempts to create a more coherent line between its narrative themes of exploration and cooperation and the mechanics the player uses to move through the simulated world. As pointed out before the game takes great care in showing the flora and fauna explored as an interactive system, which Ellery continuously pointing

out how one species of the planet interacts with others. The fiction of the game that is set up here seems to move towards what Boxall names as one of the strengths of mimesis, namely that it can create a reality that is fully existent in itself, completely disconnected from the audience (7). In the case of *In Other Waters*, the fact that the ecosystem explored is explicitly stated to function within itself, without any interactions from the player, develops a similar theme. That video games are exceedingly adept at simulating this kind of complete world has also been noted by Linda Hutcheon, who uses the term 'heterocosm' to describe their capability to simulate a complex, complete world that can be explored in its entirety by the audience (14).

Simulation, however, might also be where the game falls short in fully utilising the affordances of its medium. The heterocosm of Gliese 667Cc is hardly simulated but mostly narrated. Where the limiting of interaction and perception work astoundingly well for the development of themes of cooperation and symbiosis they seem to become a hindrance as it comes to utilising it to further the theme of independent activity in the absence of the player. Since the game only has very few moving elements, especially when no input by the player is given, *In Other Waters* misses an opportunity to show a world that moves on its own. However, the game is not fully devoid of any modes that can be understood as utilising the mechanics of simulation inherent to gameplay. As the player learns how the different spores and small creatures of the oceans of Gliese interact they can collect and manipulate them in a limited manner to change the surroundings to the player's advantage. A common mechanic carried throughout the whole game for example is the opening of blockades by plants through the activation of certain spores that cause them to retract, or using certain spores to oxygenate areas that would be otherwise dangerous to navigate. Through teaching the player these kinds of natural interactions and allowing them to use their increasing understanding of the relationships within the ecosystem to manipulate their surroundings in a non-destructive but still advantageous manner the game rewards the player for gaining knowledge of the inner workings of Gliese 667Cc. The only cases in which destructive measures are necessary to progress are when AI and Ellery navigate the remains of human structures and have to move beyond the dead, foreign steel structures they set up.

Another case in which the gameplay mechanics complicate the non-invasive approach *In Other Waters* mostly communicates is found in the fact that the AI has to feed the spores and microbes they collect, and which are in other places used to manipulate the surroundings in the productive ways described above, into the diving suit to fuel it or to restore oxygen in dangerous areas. Using spores and microbes as a resource in certain moments of danger could be understood as negotiating that sometimes there has to be made a value judgement about self-preservation and

the preservation of others but unfortunately the fiction of the game does nothing to complicate the relationship between Ellery's drive to preserve the life of Gliese 667Cc and the AI having to utilise it as a resource.

A small concession in this direction can be seen in the way that understanding the ecosystem of Glieses can sometimes become more useful than the mere consumption of resources. When navigating the aftermath of the near-extinction event, which left a large area devoid of oxygen and therefore forces the player to use spores as a source of oxygen, it can be more productive to set a certain kind of spore free in specific areas, where they will then create a small bubble of oxygenated water which, unlike the tank of the suit, is infinite and can thus create safe space. In interactions such as this, it can become more effective to understand the inner workings of the relations between certain parts of Gliese's ecosystem than to just use up all resources found for short-term profit. Still, while for example, these bubbles of air are technically superior, they are stationary and can not be used to fill up the oxygen tank of the suit once the player will have to leave them, so while the underlying mechanic is interesting and can be read in productive ways, the actual use for the player stays limited, meaning that it might be questionable how far they will interact with a mechanic such as this. Consequently, the actual gameplay mechanics and simulations might offer some interesting aspects and concepts but the limited modes of actual interaction and sometimes lacking utility mean that they do not always fully succeed in supporting the themes set up by the other elements of the game, which are geared towards an almost childlike wonder at the inherently valuable life on Gliese 667Cc and the wish to preserve it.

A reading of the game decidedly pointing towards this wonder at and appreciation of non-sentient life becomes again stronger once the narrative development of the plot is taken into account. As Ellery's search for Minae comes to a close and both the AI and the marine biologist gain a deeper understanding of the events that occurred on Gliese 667Cc before Ellery's arrival it becomes clear that this state of wonder is not to be considered the default reaction of humanity when they come into contact with other life forms. As it turns out the company that both Ellery and Minae previously worked for, and which Ellery left as a result of differences in their ideologies, had already discovered the life on Gliese 667Cc. More than that, they are the ones responsible for the near-cataclysm that Ellery and the AI already uncovered during their initial search for Minae, which was the unintended outcome of a series of experiments by the company meant to find ways to exploit the resources on this planet to support an, according to Ellery, declining Earth. In juxtaposing these two ideologies, one of observation and research and the other focused on the acquisition of resources to uphold the status quo, *In Other Waters* negotiates what can be considered

the preferred mode of interaction with non-sentient life. That one of these modes, that of exploitation of natural resources, lead to cataclysmic events and apparently to the near-extinction of what might be a sentient species leaves no doubt which side *In Other Waters* takes in this discourse. Ellery's fascination with animal and plant life as well as the depiction and partial simulation of an interlocking and complex ecosystem allow for the game to develop a narrative that decentres human agency and interaction and by this stressing the value of non-human, non-sentient life.

Ellery's declaration at the end of the game that she will try to catalogue as much of Gliese 667Cc's ecosystem before more people arrive and will, more than likely, proceed to destroy it, shows that human interaction that is not rooted in an appreciation of non-human life is considered by the game to be an inevitably destructive influence. That Ellery frames this in her comments as a continuation of the behaviour that brought the Earth of *In Other Waters* into the decrepit state it currently is in communicates that this behaviour is a current danger and that as long as the upholding of the status quo stays central to the actions of humanity they will continue to be a destructive influence. By showing this connection as having a long history and projecting it into the future the game applies ideas of the concept of futurity to underscore the ecocritical themes it contains. The way it achieves this will be the focus of my following considerations.

6. Futurity and Ecocriticism

In *Futurity: Contemporary Literature and the Quest for the Past* Amir Eshel talks about how the novel is capable of exposing the reader to the experiences of the other and as a result can extend the world they can imagine and consider (9). He uses this capability as a foundation for an understanding of futurity in which literature can connect the past to the present of the reader and consequently create conjectures about possible futures (10). This conception of futurity as a consideration of the interconnections between past, present, and future, that can expand the imaginative horizon of the reader is connected to the themes of *In Other Waters* in two ways: for one the ecocritical content the fiction of the game develops is very much presented as a worry about the expected future of the ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc. Its destruction seems inevitable to Ellery due to the present behaviour of humanity, which is necessitated by the mistakes of the past which led Earth into its current precarious situation. Further, Eshel specifically points out that his understanding of futurity is based on the personal effects that reading can have on the audience and how this can lead to changes in perspective. The concept of prosthetic affect, the ability of the audience to experience the feelings of another on their body through the interaction with a video

game very much supports this function and as a result, it stands to argue that a video game like *In Other Waters* is predisposed to create the effects Eshel ascribes to futurity.

A notable divergence from the examples used by Eshel, such as *Austerlitz* and *Hevzekim*, next to the obvious difference in medium, is that *In Other Waters* is a science fiction story. However, its genre does not stop the game from working along the same lines as Eshel, describes. The narrative still sets up a present point of relation, in this case, a future in which space travel and AI have become so commonplace that Ellery feels no need to comment on it, and relates this to an expected future, here the assumed destruction of the ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc, which is the result of a continuation of past behaviour. The meaningful reconfiguration that the genre and the resulting shifts in time bring with them is that the past which has led to the dire situation of the narrative is at the same time implied to be the present of the reader. Where Heshel considers how past events have shaped the present and where this might lead, *In Other Waters* asks the player to imagine a future that is based on the continuation of present behaviour, a question that also occupies space in Eshel's considerations, as he names modernity to be defined by a sense of dread towards the future (1). A feeling very much present in the eco-crisis of *In Other Waters*, which, to Boxall, seems almost implied in the genre of science fiction, as he calls eco-crisis the “ugly twin of technicity, the blowback of the human domination of nature” (12).

So it makes sense that *In Other Waters*, a science fiction video game, might consider the interlinks between present behaviour and future crisis and that the player would feel these themes spread throughout the game both in its fiction and its gameplay. For the fiction elements in the game, this is most directly depicted in the aftermath of the near extinction caused by human research on the planet and the hostile environment created as a result. The inherent danger to the ecosystem posed by human actions is also heavily implied in Ellery's comments and reactions to finding life on Gliese in the first place. Not only does she state that people will continue to make the same mistakes that devastated Earth in the first place but her immediate push towards cataloguing and preserving the life she finds is also indicative of the low opinion she holds of humanity in these regards: it is telling that her first thought at seeing alien life seems to be “ I need to write all of this down before we destroy it as well.”

The gameplay also carries some of the weight of the ecocritical elements of *In Other Waters*, as almost all sources of danger that the game confronts the player with are the result of human interaction. The life-threatening remains of the extinction event and the de-oxygenated ruins of the research facilities Ellery and the AI explore are not dangers inherent to Gliese 667Cc but what is left after the destruction humanity has brought with it. By lacking any indigenous predators for the

player to fight off *In Other Waters* uses interactions with the game's mechanics to communicate to the player that more often than not humanity has created the things that threaten it themselves. And this is often specifically about the extinction of species that have been caused by people.

In pointing this out the game goes against an almost constant attribute of flora and fauna in video games that both Chang in her essay on farm games and van Ooijen in his analysis of depictions of hunting in video games point out: the lack of degradation (Chang 246) and its infinity (van Ooijen 41). Both explain that the mechanics of a game usually soften the implied impact of human interaction on ecosystems by making it impossible for the player to completely exhaust the natural resources around them. Thus players are never really encouraged to consider the impact their interactions have on the environment. Games that do offer limited resources often make sure that there is exactly enough of a given object in the world for the player to be able to achieve all of their objectives to make sure that they are not frustrated at a later point. A notable exception here is often strategy games, in which the struggle over limited resources is a common theme, but even here the problem framed as the most pressing is other factions using up resources needed by the player, not the consequences of the player's action having them deplete the resources they would need themselves to a dangerous degree.

The fictional aspect of *In Other Waters* is full of signs of the finite nature of life and whole species. The most high-profile of these might be considered to be the assumed disappearance of the Artificers since they might be sentient and as such a possible meeting could offer fascinating interactions for the player, but also the destruction of non-sentient life plays an important role and is depicted as a devastating loss by the game. The resulting badlands are the result of the research of the human facilities which has, by creating a chain reaction of extinction in the flora and fauna of Gliese 667Cc created a hostile environment that poses a great risk to traverse for Ellery.

Mechanically the finite nature of nature is also present, with microbes and spores collected by the player not replenishing, thus giving greater weight to their consumption. However, as mentioned above, there will almost always be enough resources for the payer to continue playing and even if they were to collect every single sample in the game they would not have any impact on the ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc, neither on a local, not a global scale. While it does make sense to argue that a single person and an AI might simply not be able to devastate a complete ecosystem on their own it still might have been interesting to see the consequences of the player's interaction to be reflected in the environments in a more lasting and possibly negative way to further deepen the ecocritical aspects of the game. Thus even if the game does try to develop modes in which it disrupts the gameplay mechanics and interactions which according to Alenda Chang in her

Manifesto for Environmental Game Design are the basis for most game development and which she calls "often fundamentally antienvironmental" (70) it does not necessarily succeed completely in this. So while the fiction does very much criticise the understanding of nature as a reserve that is common and criticised by Chang (71), the gameplay still has the player often interact with the environment as exactly that: a reserve of microbes and spores necessary to navigate the space of the game successfully. It is however an important step that the interactions themselves are not necessarily framed as consumption but also often happens as the player encouraging different parts of Gliese's ecosystem to interact in the way it would normally do, just on another scale. Here the game shows a willingness to develop the wider range of possible player interactions with the environment that Chang names as necessary for video games to fully utilise their ecocritical potential (73).

Still, *In Other Water's* fiction focusing on the way that a limited interaction of humanity with an ecosystem that was not fully understood and how the gameplay requires the player to learn the interaction of this system to navigate these spaces in a non-destructive way does have meaning in relation to an observation by Megan Condis in her analysis of *Horizon Zero Dawn* and *Heaven's Vault* as ecocritical games. Here she notes that one of the greatest strengths of *Heaven's Vault* is the fact that it does not create an enemy which serves as a direct threat but instead has the player realise that an entire system of preferences and behaviours has to lead to the destruction of societies. *In Other Waters* does this as well, with the extinction of the life on Gliese not being represented through some singular entity or group but instead through a whole area, which itself has turned into a danger for all life and it is the specific absence of flora and fauna here that is the reason for the hostile environment. Thus there is a threat that is represented through a system, both in the breaking down of a beneficial one, as well as the occurrence of a new, hostile order. Preferences also play an important role in this, as the extinction is the result of human behaviour, specifically the preference to continue a current system, even if it is known in the long run to have negative outcomes as a whole. As Ellery points out to the AI, the current behaviour of humanity has already had disastrous consequences in creating an Earth so hostile that support through other planets has become necessary but even more than that, once life on another planet is discovered this does not lead to a reconsideration of the current system of preferences but a complete reproduction of them on Gliese 667Cc. The upholding and repetition of the current system have then, as the near extinction in the oceans and the disappearance of the Artificers show, the same ramifications.

7. Conclusion

Over the course of this analysis, I have taken a deeper look into the way that fiction and gameplay mechanics interact in 2020's *In Other Waters*. The main objective in this was to interrogate whether the video game uses the affordances of its medium effectively to develop a coherent theming in which the concept of futurity as it has been used by Amir Eshel, meaning the interconnection between past, present and future to set up conjectures about the future. In this, the most important narrative divergence from Eshel's typology was the fact that *In Other Waters* is a science fiction narrative, by this shifting the narrative levels. Still, as has been shown in this analysis, the general direction of the argument holds up, as the productive interconnection between past, present, and future stays intact. It might even be argued that the call to action this structure might contain is more urgent in future fiction, as here the negative behaviour of the past that is carried into the future and continues its destructive trajectory there is the presence of the audience.

That the player's feelings concerning the fiction of the narrative are this strong has also been connected to how the medium of the video game forces the player to interact with the content of a narrative both on an intellectual level to understand the mechanics and by this motivating them to see the problems they are encountering not as the result of individual action but of systemic hardships, which can only be understood and solved by grasping the system encountered in full. Another important element in this is how the player is physically interacting with the medium in multiple ways, both through aural, visual, but also haptic modes through the controls. That this means that the experience of the game leads to the creation of an embodied event that is inscribed upon the player has been conceptualised here along the lines of Alison Landsberg's prosthetic memory and Peter Boxall's prosthetic imagination. However, to centre, the importance of emotional processes in the case of video games the term of prosthetic affect has been developed and applied. The objective in this was to show how *In Other Waters* can create a narrative and thematic mood in the player through how it mediates the experiences of an AI by having all aesthetic experiences be the result of second-hand narration and also the simple and repetitive gameplay of traversing the depths of Gliese 667Cc.

Another important element that can be highlighted through these structures of futurity and prosthetic affect are the ecocritical content of *In Other Waters*. By having the narrating character Ellery Vas stress the dejected state of Earth and in connection voicing her conviction that the same fate would befall Gliese 667Cc if it ever were to become home to a human population the fiction of *In Other Waters* centres the destructive effect humanity has on their surroundings. To exemplify this

the game has Ellery communicate the flora and fauna of the oceans she is travelling from her perspective as a marine biologist, consequently pointing out the symbiotic relations between the numerous life forms she encounters. Thus the game presents Gliese 667Cc as a closed system that carries itself without human interaction. More so, the uncovering of the past events on the planet stresses again the destructive influence mankind has. On the gameplay side, there is a focus on exploration and observation, which especially through Ellery's enthusiastic voice gains a perspective that can depict the life forms encountered as inherently valuable, disconnected from any uses to the player. This is further increased by the fact that the life of Gliese 667Cc is non-sentient, meaning that the implication of future profits is further reduced. That the mechanics of the game then force the player to consume some of these creatures is an unfortunate side effect of the game attempting to create tension through gameplay. Ultimately these consumptions disrupt the theme of symbiosis and distant observation that is otherwise presented in the game's fiction, especially since the microbes and spores gathered by the player are framed as non-infinite and vital to the ecosystem of Gliese 667Cc. Consequently, the game inadvertently repeats the 'nature as reserve' that Alenda Chang already criticised in her analysis of farm games.

The result of these considerations is that *In Other Waters* is an effective, if not perfect, example of the narrative and thematic capabilities of video games as a medium. The interplay between the hypermedial mode where much of its visual elements are conveyed through text and which uses simple icons on a screen and a set of non-trivial but also non-challenging inputs that create a certain mood, what Condis calls the affect of a game, which can support the contemplative elements of its narrative. While it has been found that the gameplay still has moments in which traditional concepts and interactions interrupt the thematic complex that is set up by the fiction of the game, this is not nearly as much the case as in most other games. Consequently, the game is not only an interesting addition to the ecocritical and posthuman discourses which utilises its affordances to greatly engage the audience both intellectually and emotionally with the questions it asks but is also an example of the sometimes impressive results afforded by the creative freedom of small-scale video games.

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